

COHERENCE AND COHESION IN WRITING

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Abstract:

This article studies what are coherence and cohesion actually, and when we can use them appropriately in the writing. The target of writing this article is giving some information about how important is using coherence and cohesion in writing.

Key words: writing comprehension, connection, linking words, synonyms, publications, academic writing, repeated words or ideas, reference words, thematic development, substitution, ellipsis

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/62ydy37>

What are coherence and cohesion in general?

Coherence and cohesion serve for adding direct ideas and connecting them with proper way in the speech or writing. Although they are needful for speaking, they have the biggest role in the writing. Writing comprehensions always should have general meaning, obvious structure and related ideas for topic. Coherence and cohesion provide these criteria in the writing. In addition, they are associated with each other. If there is not one of them in the writing, the reader cannot understand the real concept clearly. For this reason, both of them are very essential for aiding readability and correct communication between the opinions and ideas. Besides that, they are also responsible for the thematic development. Of course, when the reader reads one of the essays or publications, he or she pays attention to its headline at first. At that time, the reader has just a little and initial meaning about the whole topic. Then he or she reads the writing with this opinion. Therefore, the writer should write the text with thematic development and do not go out of topic. Also, it causes to broke the coherence and cohesion in writing.

Where is difference between both of them?

Separating coherence and cohesion is slight complicated. Because, their concern is so similar with each other. In general, coherence is the correspondence to the one of reports. For example, there are a lot of writing types also their themes are dissimilar. To know how use the appropriate opinion or statistics is coherence. Namely, coherence is much more duty to make everything flow smoothly. When ideas and opinions are added correctly, the coherence is achieved in the writing.

In contrast, cohesion is the words that connect the sentences adequately. That is, using the definite logical bridges, synonyms, linking words in writing is cohesion. This is another important feature to reach the general meaning in the

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essays. To write cohesive essay, the writer has to give concentration to these main methods:

- repeated words or ideas;
- reference words;
- transitional signals;
- substitution;
- ellipsis;

Repeated words or ideas. This is one of the ways for achieving the cohesion in the writing. Obviously, most of students consider that repeat the same word or conjunction is not proper for writing. That's exactly right, because we repeat the matching words again and again it must be affected to the losing of cohesion in writing. Admittedly, finding synonyms will be a bit complicated for some students during writing. However, not repeat and to change just word form is the best way for saving time from thinking of some difficult synonyms and keeping the real meaning of essay. For instance:

“In academic writing every idea should be planned. Because, the plan helps to be coherent and meaningful.”

Reference words. These words or phrases helps to refer to something which is mentioned earliest in the text. It can be name, place and grammatical rule. The common version of reference words is pronouns. Pronouns need exchange the name of the first thing in the writing. For example:

“Reading different books is very useful activity for our brain. It can aid to widen the outlook.”

Using this method in the writing, gives being coherent and cohesive. And, the reader is not bored during reading it.

Transitional signals. This type also called linking words or cohesive devices. Linking words assist to connect the words, phrases or sentences and make relationship between them. If the transitional signals namely, linking words are used in the writing, general meaning and thematic development will be appeared distinctly. Samples of transitional signals:

- at first - for beginning the paragraph;
- in addition - to add other opinions;
- because - used for explaining the reason;
- however - used for making a contrast idea;
- for example - used for including samples;
- in conclusion - to concluding the writing;

Substitution. This method means using one word or phrase to replace another word which is written earlier. Admittedly, it is so resembled with reference words, however there is just small difference that is, the reference words always use after the main thing which is texted earlier and they are expressed with pronouns. But the substitution is usually limited to the clause which follows the words being exchanged. Moreover, *one*, *so* and auxiliary verbs like *do*, *have*, and *be*, especially used as substitutions during writing something. For example:

“Strolling in the morning is very simple and useful activity for our health, doing so can exercise our body also.”

Ellipsis indicates omitting one word our several words which is already evident in the text. Sometimes it is called like *substitution by zero* because ellipsis does not substitute with any word taking its place. It can be more obvious with this example:

“Apple is one of the handy fruits among others. The first importance of it is the healthiest fruit for our teeth. The second is also beneficial for increasing of blood in the organism.”

Samples & Synonyms

As I mentioned before, there will be several and variety of opinions in one writing. For example, we will have ideas which should be connected parallel or sometimes we must link the sentences with subordinating conjunctions. Of course, it happens because of the writing content. On that time, linking words, conjunctions and phrases come to assist for adding or connecting the thoughts in the writing. And here is a table which is shown such samples of linking words.

Type	Examples
To add personal opinion:	<i>In my own opinion; to my mind; in my view; I suppose that; I strongly believe that...</i>
For listing the ideas:	<i>Firstly; to begin with; first of all; Secondly; then; next; after this/that; Finally; lastly;</i>
To show cause:	<i>Because; as; since; due to the fact that; for this reason;</i>
To show result:	<i>Therefore; consequently; as a consequence; as a result; so;</i>
For showing purpose:	<i>So that; in order to;</i>
To give samples:	<i>For example; for instance; such as; like;</i>
For adding more ideas to the one topic:	<i>Besides that/this; furthermore; moreover; apart from this/that; in addition to;</i>
To show contrast:	<i>But; however; yet; nevertheless; nonetheless; although; even though; in spite of; despite of;</i>
For concluding:	<i>In conclusion; to sum up; on the whole; all in all;</i>

How are they essential in academic writing?

Coherence and cohesion have the large influence for the academic writing. In other words, academic writing paragraphs have to be coherent and cohesive. To achieve coherence and cohesion, our sentences need to connect in a logical way with each other so that the reader understand clearly the development of our ideas and mainly what we want to say. It will be easy to evaluate for them if our essay is linked with clarity. If we use one-word, cohesive device or even idea wrongly, it can be reason for losing the main content from the essay and taking the lower mark. Therefore, in IELTS and TOEFL tests 25% of score is given because of having coherence and cohesion in the writing.

Instructor and examiner Kies gave this advice about coherence:

“Coherence is a product of many different factors, which combine to make every paragraph, every sentence, and every phrase contribute to the meaning of the whole piece. Coherence in writing is much more difficult to sustain than coherent speech simply because writers have no nonverbal clues to inform if their message is clear or not. Therefore, writers must make their patterns of coherence more explicit and much more carefully planned. Coherence itself is the product or two factors – paragraph unity and sentence cohesion.”

All in all, coherence and cohesion are inherent patterns in the writing types. They are so essential for writing the readable and expressive essays or publications. Then, the writer should know the structure of adding the true ideas and using transitional signals. Thereby, any type of writing will be coherent and cohesive by understanding the formation of writing paragraphs.

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